

NANOCELLULOSE REINFORCED BIO-POLYURETHANE FOAMS AS CORE IN SANDWICH COMPOSITE PANELS

Nikolina Frisk^{1,2}, Mohini Sain^{1,2} and Kristiina Oksman^{1,2}

¹ Division of Materials Science, Luleå University of Technology, SE 97187 Luleå Sweden

² Centre for Biocomposites and Biomaterials Processing, Faculty of Forestry, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada

Kristiina.Oksman@ltu.se

msain@utoronto.ca

Keywords: Bio polyurethane; nanocomposite foam; mechanical properties; microstructure; cellulose nanofibers; sandwich laminate; X-ray tomography; vacuum infusion.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this work was to reinforce bio-polyurethane (BPU) with cellulose nanofibers (CNF) to develop foams suitable for use as core in lightweight composite panels. The nanofibers were prepared using mechanical grinding of bleached carrot juice residue, a cheap and energy efficient process. The prepared foam properties were studied and compared to neat BPU foam properties. The results showed that the CNF reinforced foam had better mechanical properties compared to the neat bio-PU foams and the addition of cellulose nanofibers decreased the cell size and open cell content. Then the foam suitability for composite use was evaluated by manufacturing lightweight sandwich panels using vacuum infusion process with CNF reinforced BPU foam core. Kraft paper was used as a skin and epoxy resin was used as adhesive resin and the composite laminates were prepared using vacuum infusion technique. These nanofiber reinforced core materials resulted in sandwich panels with improved mechanical properties. X-ray tomography showed that the resin did not penetrate into the core but only the foam surface layer. Moreover, the results were evaluated in a material selection process by means of minimizing merit indices. A trend in the behaviour of compressive properties of the foam and flexural properties of the sandwich panels could be established. The addition of small amount of cellulose nanofibers to BPU based foams is leading to a foam which have similar properties as commercial rigid PU foams.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the last years the use of biobased polyols for polyurethane (PU) foams has attracted attention because of the renewable raw material resources [1-6]. However, biobased polyurethane (BPU) foams are not yet used for commercial applications because they do not meet industrial requirements for compression strength which should be ≥ 180 kPa [1]. Different reinforcements have been used to improve the foam properties, for example wood fibers, clay, cellulose nanocrystals and cellulose nanofibers [2-6]. We have for example shown that cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) are promising reinforcement for palm oil based BPU foams. The compressive modulus and strength of BPU nanocomposite foam were improved with 216 % and 117 % respectively by addition of small amount of cellulose nanocrystals (1.6 wt%) [6].

In this study we are comparing CNF reinforced BPU foams with a non-reinforced BPU foams in manufacturing of sandwich composites. The goal is to obtain a BPU foam with higher mechanical performance than the unreinforced ones and investigate the effect of the CNF addition on the final sandwich structure.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Component	Materials	Task
Polyol	Castor oil (Jagropol-400). Jayant Agro-Organtics LTD, India. Functionality: 3 and OH-value: 0.35 gKOH/g	The resin base
Isocyanate	Polymeric methane diphenyl isocyanate, pMDI (Rubinate M). Huntsman Corporation, West Point, GA, USA Functionality: 2.7, NCO: 31 %	The reactive pre-polymer.
Blowing agent	Water	React with isocyanate group, initiate foaming
Surfactant	Polysiloxane (DABCO DC 5357). Air Products, Canada	Reduce the surface tension
Catalyst	N,N-Bis[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]-N,N-dimethylpropane-1,3-diamine (Polycat 9) and dipropylene glycol-triethylenediamine (DABCO 33 LV), Air Products, Canada	Balance the blowing and the cross-linking reaction
Others	Wet cellulose nanofibers, LTU, Sweden. 8 wt% CNF in water	Reinforcements

Table 1: Raw materials and their role in the preparation of BPU foams.

The used cellulose nanofibers were mechanically separated from bleached carrot juice residue, the process is described elsewhere [8]. The nanofiber widths are approximately 10-20 nm and the length is estimated to be at micrometer level. These nanofibers are easily dispersed in water as they are hydrophilic but aggregated if dried and here we have used them in wet form. The water in the suspension is acting as blowing agent.

The preparation of the BPU foams, nanocomposite foams and the sandwich panels are described in detail in Frisk et al [5], briefly the wet cellulose nanofibers were mixed with castor oil polyol, after that the additives and the reactive pMDI were mixed, as shown in Figure 1. The cellulose nanofiber content in the final foam was approximately 0.15wt%. BPU foams with four different densities were prepared, 35, 40, 45 and 50 kg/m³, the density was controlled with water blowing agent [5].

Figure 1. Schematic presentation of the BPU-foam preparation process [5].

The BPU-foams with varied density with and without CNF were used as core in the sandwich panels which were prepared using vacuum infusion as seen in the Figure 2. Epoxy was used as resin and kraft paper as skin.

Figure 2. Vacuum infusion of cellulose nanofiber reinforced BPU core covered by Kraft paper skin and b) a schematic of the sandwich design.

The open cell content, density, cell size and compressive properties of the BPU foams were studied. The flexural properties, microstructure, resin penetration and facing strength were evaluated of the sandwich panels. Further more, the prepared foams and panels were ranked for best performance using materials indices. More information of the testing procedures is found in Frisk et al 2017 [5]

3. RESULTS

Table 2 shows the comparison of the mechanical properties of the BPU, BPU-CNF foams as well as their sandwich panels. The addition of CF is improved the mechanical properties of the foams and this addition is also positively affecting flexural properties of the sandwich panels. The BPU-CNF foam with lowest density is showing highest improvements.

Density (kg/m ³)	Type	Compressive properties		Flexural properties	
		Strength (kPa)	Modulus (MPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (MPa)
35	BPU-CNF	252 ± 7	5.0 ± 0.3	5.8 ± 0.5	410 ± 4
	BPU	179 ± 7	3.4 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	155 ± 10
40	BPU-CNF	242 ± 10	5.7 ± 0.5	2.4 ± 0.4	163 ± 11
	BPU	225 ± 6	4.7 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.3	159 ± 11
45	BPU-CNF	282 ± 16	6.6 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.3	186 ± 8
	BPU	234 ± 19	5.0 ± 0.5	1.7 ± 0.2	135 ± 9
50	BPU-CNF	303 ± 21	6.1 ± 0.2	3.1 ± 1.4	202 ± 40
	BPU	266 ± 17	6.3 ± 0.4	2.7 ± 0.2	166 ± 15

Table 2: Comparison of the compressive properties of the BPU foams with and without CNF and flexural properties of the sandwich panels.

Figure 3 is showing the sandwich panels as well as the comparison of the properties with commercial PU foams.

Figure 3: a) Sandwich laminates with cellulose nanofiber reinforced bio-PU core and cellulose fiber skin and b) materials properties compared with commercial PU foams.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of the cellulose nanofibers on bio-PU core as well as on the final sandwich laminates with different densities are summarized in the Table 3. The results indicate that the mechanical

properties of the bio-PU foam were improved by reinforcing the pre-resin with small amounts (0.13-0.17wt%) of wet carrot CNF. The laminates with lowest density (35 kg/m³) the highest CNF content 0.17wt% showed the best properties and showed highest effect of the addition of cellulose nanofibers. The flexural modulus and strength improved with 163 respective 167% with the presence of CNF.

Material property	$\rho=35$ BPUCNF	$\rho=40$ BPUCNF	$\rho=45$ BPUCNF	$\rho=50$ BPUCNF
Cell size	- 18 %	- 19 %	- 19 %	- 18 %
Open cell content	- 51 %	0 %	- 18 %	- 7 %
Compressive strength	+ 41 %	+ 8 %	+ 21 %	+ 14 %
Compressive modulus	+ 46 %	+ 21 %	+ 31 %	0 %
Flexural strength	+ 167 %	+ 2 %	+ 72 %	+ 14 %
Flexural modulus	+ 163 %	+ 3 %	+ 38 %	+ 21 %
Facing strength	+ 88 %	+ 37 %	+ 53 %	+ 42 %

Table3: Summarizing of the influence of cellulose nanofiber reinforce core with different density (35, 40, 45, 50 kg/m³) and sandwich laminate properties.

Ultimately, this work shows a positive trend suggesting CNF-reinforced BPU foam has a great potential for use in commercialized products or structural components where the eco-friendly raw materials and lightweight are targeted.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support under INCOM EC FP7, Grant agreement No: 608746

REFERENCES

- [1] Gu R, Konar S, Sain M. Preparation and characterization of sustainable polyurethane foams from soybean oils. *Journal of American Oil Chemists' Society* 89 (2012) 2103-2111.
- [2] Gu R, Sain MM, Konar SK. A feasibility study of polyurethane composite foam with added hardwood pulp. *Industrial Crops and Products* 42 (2013) 273-279.
- [3] Zhu M, Bandyopadhyay-Ghosh S, Khazabi M, Cai H, Correa C, Sain M. Reinforcement of soy polyol-based rigid polyurethane foams by cellulose microfibrils and nanoclays. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 124 (2012) 4702-4710.
- [4] Oksman K, Aitomäki Y, Mathew AP, Siqueira G, Zhou Q, Butylina S, Tanpichai S, Zhou X, Hooshmand S. Review of the recent developments in cellulose nanocomposite processing, *Composites Part A* 83 (2016) 2-18.
- [5] Frisk N, Sain M, Oksman K. *Novel applications of nanocellulose: Lightweight sandwich composites for transportation in Reference Module of Materials Science and Materials Engineering, April (2017).*
- [6] Zhou X, Sain M, Oksman K, Semi-rigid biopolyurethane foams based on palm-oil polyol and reinforced with cellulose nanocrystals, *Composites Part A* 83 (2016) 56-62.
- [7] Zhou X, Sethi J, Berglund L, Aitomäki Y, Frisk N, Sain MM, Oksman K. Dispersion and reinforcing effect of carrot nanofibers on biopolyurethane foams. *Materials Design* 110 (2016) 526-531.
- [8] Berglund L, Noel M, Aitomäki Y, Öman T, Oksman K. Production potential of cellulose nanofibers from industrial residues: Efficiency and nanofiber characteristics. *Industrial Crops and Products* 92 (2016) 84-92.